

Introduction

This document describes “Impact Screening”, an analytical process to provide early warning signals when an intervention may have little to no impact.

Impact Screening is designed to:

- Leverage pre-existing data streams to eliminate the need for data collection or cleaning
- Rapidly rule out the presence of causal impact in the vast majority of instances
- Serve as a sector-agnostic, entry level approach to producing causal evidence with minimal configuration.
- Exhibit the kind of modularity that allows for automation of contextual configuration.

We hope to apply this technique to detect trend anomalies in places where a treatment has been applied, allowing for preliminary corroboration of effectiveness. This is currently being prototyped for agricultural treatment outcomes.

Assumptions: We are interested in an outcome (e.g. higher yield of a crop) and suppose that there are indicators (e.g. the yield of that crop) which can be quantified by proxy variables (e.g. a satellite-derived vegetation density scoring function, like NDVI).

- If an indicator is known to induce changes to a proxy variable, a change in that indicator must produce a change in the proxy
- Detecting an unusual change in a proxy is indicative of a plausible unusual change in an associated indicator of this sort
- The absence of a change in the proxy is indicative of the absence of plausible change in the indicator
- Comprehensive, live updated data sets of proxies exist (vegetation density, administrative data, transaction records)
- We can detect unusual changes in proxies as a rough test of whether an indicator has been affected by an activity
- The stronger the correlation between the indicator and the proxy, the smaller a change will produce a noticeable change in the proxy

Requirements:

- We want to detect the presence or absence of unusual changes in a proxy as a way to assess quickly and cheaply whether or not an activity is producing an expected change in an outcome indicator.
- Problems:
 - We need to confirm that the change is “unusual”. This is achieved with counterfactual comparison.
 - The amount of change in the proxy may not map cleanly to an amount of change in a proxy
 - A single data point is not adequate to draw a conclusion.
 - We need to control for confounding variables that may make a treatment site act differently from a counterfactual or vice versa

- Counterfactuals need to be adequately similar to the treatment for legitimate comparison
- Seasonality is a key confounder that must be accounted for.
- We want to detect whether an effect is present quickly and update continuously.

Methodology Overview:

- We seek to report the “level of unusualness” of the treatment group's behavior. An unusual change is a sign that something uniquely present in the treatment group is causing a change, plausibly the treatment itself. We avoid quantifying an effect size because the exact relationship is unmapped.
 - A lack of unusual behaviour is a sign that causal impact is unlikely.
- We compare the treatment to both its historical behaviour and the behaviour of similar groups
 - We select comparisons by assessing similarity and relevance criteria, and by ranking comparisons on a weighted composite similarity score (60% correlatedness, 40% variance scale). The relevant comparisons above a set score cutoff are included in the analysis.
 - We select proximate comparison groups to increase the probability that background factors are shared with the treatment.
- To manage seasonality, we turn a full longitudinal data set into panel data and index panels to a corresponding calendar date.
 - Each year is divided into intervals and data is aggregated within each interval.
 - Intervals are compared to their equivalent across years.
- To normalize across heterogeneous groups and simultaneously compare to past behaviour, we calculate a baseline for each area and assess percent change from that baseline for each panel.
- To report the unusualness of the treatment's behaviour, for each panel we then construct a distribution of those percent change values from the comparisons, and report what the percentile of the treatment would be on that distribution.
 - We determine historical baseline for each interval in each group (comparisons and treatment) by calculating the median value of a set number of years before a date of expected visible change from the treatment. This baseline is used throughout post-impact years and is not updated to include any intervals after the treatment.
- To reduce sensitivity to individual anomalous intervals, observations are grouped into rolling windows of a set number of consecutive intervals. Within each window, each area's performance is summarized by its lower quartile per-interval percentile value; a conservative measure that requires consistent positive deviation rather than a single spike. The treatment area's window summary is then ranked against the same metric across all comparison areas, producing a new percentile as a final test statistic for that window. As new intervals become available, the window advances and the statistic is recalculated, generating a time series that tracks whether an anomalous trend is persisting.

Current implementation:

- This has been optimized for the use of vegetation indicators for agricultural productivity.
- Intervals are set at 15 days to contain three data captures from sentinel-2, the source of satellite data. This allows for mosaicing of non occluded pixels, mitigating risk of cloud cover.
- Input designates crop, a relevant observation period during which growth is visible, a date that changes would begin to occur from activities, and a geographic location that the treatment is applied
- A 5km buffer around the treatment is applied to manage risk of treatment spillage. A ring is generated with the inner perimeter at the outer border of the buffer. The ring is 30km in width and is gridded into squares of 9km² in area. Squares more than 30% outside of the ring are dropped. (Leaves about 450 candidates for comparison)

- A relevant indicator is selected based on crop.
 - NDVI for wheat
 - NDVI in early season and EVI at saturation for maize.
 - NDVI in early season for cotton and NDRE at flowering.
 - MCARI for coffee and cocoa
- Selected indicator data for the observation period is pulled for each candidate and the treatment for 5 years before the date of impact and for all years after. Data also includes percent cloud occlusion and percent vegetation coverage. (Sentinel-2 was launched in 2015, so the earliest usable date of impact is 01/01/2021)
 - Treatment area has a cropland mask applied to only report agricultural pixels for vegetation that exhibits crop-like growth cycles.

- Comparisons are filtered out based on adequate presence of vegetation and high enough proportion of unoccluded captures. Remaining captures are ranged by similarity score at a .85 cutoff. If fewer than 30 comparisons qualify, the best candidates are drawn from below the cutoff until 30 are selected.

- Baselines are calculated for each interval in the observation window for each area.
- Comparison percent change from baseline is constructed for each interval and treatment percentile is reported.

Click on any time period in the chart to see how your selected area compares to the surrounding comparison grid squares.

Your Selected Area

+100.4%

change from baseline

Percentile Rank

98%

Probable Impact

Comparison Grid Squares

47 comparison grid squares selected

Square 1: +42.3%	Square 2: -21.1%	Square 3: -9.9%	Square 4: -29.2%	Square 5: -17.5%
Square 6: +25.0%	Square 7: -29.7%	Square 8: +1.4%	Square 9: -33.5%	Square 10: -19.3%
Square 11: +6.5%	Square 12: -18.8%	Square 13: +6.2%	Square 14: +7.8%	Square 15: +9.9%
Square 16: +34.0%	Square 17: -21.1%	Square 18: -6.1%	Square 19: -51.7%	Square 20: -26.7%
Square 21: +72.3%	Square 22: +53.4%	Square 23: +40.4%	Square 24: +96.1%	
Square 25: -47.8%	Square 26: -48.4%	Square 27: -44.4%	Square 28: +39.0%	
Square 29: +42.8%	Square 30: -21.5%	Square 31: +45.8%	Square 32: -40.5%	
Square 33: -34.2%	Square 34: +35.0%	Square 35: -30.8%	Square 36: +51.4%	
Square 37: -33.3%	Square 38: +22.4%	Square 39: +9.1%	Square 40: -15.2%	
Square 41: +69.2%	Square 42: +2.8%	Square 43: +2.2%	Square 44: -45.3%	
Square 45: +130.8%	Square 46: +21.0%	Square 47: -16.8%		

- Windows are constructed from 4 contiguous intervals. Each comparison compares its percentile from the per interval distribution and reports the second lowest value. New distribution constructed from those comparison percentiles

and the treatment compares its second lowest value to that distribution and reports a percentile.

- Treatment percentile is the final test statistic for a panel.
- As new data emerges, windows move forward, adding next interval and removing earliest, then recalculating. Construct a time series of treatment test statistics to show persistence of abnormal trend presence.
- As a general rule, >95% is not common for test statistic. To rule out failure quickly, a 80% value is a good decision threshold, associated with a 20% false positive rate.

Advantages:

- This is fast, indicating the absence of causative impact within 60 days of expected impact.
- This is scalable, and can be reapplied through pre-built algorithms. It does not require field data collection, and is reported from independent, objective sources.
- This is generalizable to other data sets containing proxies.
- The end output is intuitive in that it is a single number and a higher number is a better signal.
- This is continuous and can automatically update with emergent data from a live feed.

Terms:

- Interval: a single observation in a time series or panel
- Window: aggregated set of intervals for longer time frame pattern analysis
- Proxy: A variable with a known correlation to the indicator of the indicator of interest. Proxies are often relevant as easier or cheaper to measure alternatives to the direct indicator.

Patent Pending — U.S. Provisional Application No. 63/931,168.